

1 **Two-Ray Reflection Resolution Algorithm for Planar**
2 **Material Electromagnetic Property Measurement at**
3 **the Millimeter-Wave Bands**

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10 **Key Points:**

- 11 • A three-step minimum least squares (MLS) based algorithm to resolve two adja-
12 cent rays reflected from the front and the back surfaces of a board-shaped mate-
13 rial is proposed.
- 14 • A closed-form expression of the Cramér-Rao lower bound (CRLB) is derived as
15 a benchmark of performance. The performance of the proposed algorithm is eval-
16 uated through comparison with the CRLB.
- 17 • Typical board-shaped building materials, including a wooden board, a plaster board,
18 and a granite board, are measured for various incident angles to validate the al-
19 gorithm.

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Abstract

Electromagnetic (EM) reflection properties of building materials and structures have been investigated through practical measurements. However, the finite thickness of measured materials makes it challenging to resolve the rays reflected from the front and the back surfaces. In this paper, we therefore present a three-step minimum least squares (MLS) based algorithm to resolve two closely adjacent rays reflected from the front and the back surfaces of a board-shaped material. Our analytical and numerical results show that the proposed algorithm achieves the Cramér-Rao lower bound (CRLB). The proposed algorithm is validated using measurement data for various materials and incident angles in the 40-50 GHz frequency band. The validation results show that the proposed algorithm is capable of resolving two closely adjacent rays with a root-mean-square deviation that is smaller than 0.08. Main applications of the proposed algorithm can be found in the frequency domain measurements of the EM wave reflections by typical building structures, e.g., window glass, doors, ceiling, floors, etc.

1 Introduction

Over 80% of mobile traffic takes place indoors and it is predicted that mobile traffic will increase by up to 1000 times in the next decade (Cisco, Accessed 2019). Therefore, modelling indoor radio propagation and wireless channel is fundamental for the design and evaluation of wireless networks (De la Roche et al., 2012). Moreover, the envisaged application of millimeter wave (mmWave) communications in future 5G/B5G networks put forward requirements on broad bandwidth indoor channel modelling (Rappaport et al., 2013; Samimi & Rappaport, 2016). Accurate mmWave indoor channel simulations are critical for the design, evaluation and deployment of future mmWave networks. The ray tracing (RT) and ray launching (RL) algorithms are commonly employed to predict the indoor radio channels (Dai et al., 2017; Casino et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2017). To support the RT/RL based indoor wireless channel simulation, the attenuation, diffraction, scattering, and reflection of electromagnetic (EM) waves by typical planar building materials has to be investigated based on measurement (Azar et al., 2014; Burnside & Burgener, 1983; Zhekov et al., 2018). Due to the finite thickness of the materials used in buildings, the measured reflection is typically comprised of multiple reflection rays. In RT/RL algorithms, the contribution of the first ray to the reflection is usually modelled applying the Fresnel's coefficients, for the sake of simplicity (Yun & Iskander, 2015; Sheikh et al., 2016). However, neglecting the high-order rays leads to inaccurate channel simulation. Fortunately, due to attenuation loss inside the material at mmWave, the high-order reflections can be neglected in comparison with the first and the second rays (See Fig. 1). Therefore, an alternative way to simulate reflections by board-shaped building materials is to simulate the two main closely adjacent rays, whose behaviour need to be characterized through measurement. In order to analyse the impact of various types of building materials on EM waves, frequency domain measurements are usually performed using a vector network analyzer (VNA) (Azar et al., 2014; Hajisaeid et al., 2018; Zhekov et al., 2018). To characterize the two rays reflected by planar building materials, the two rays have to be resolved from measurement data.

Moreover, EM properties of planar building materials have been characterized through VNA-based measurements (Sagnard et al., 2005b, 2005a; Martin et al., 2017; Degli-Esposti et al., 2017; Hajisaeid et al., 2018). Nevertheless, accurate measurements of EM properties, e.g. the complex permittivity, of building materials is challenging in an open space environment (Ahmadi-Shokouh et al., 2009, 2011). In some state-of-the-art literature, multiple reflections inside the planar material have been considered in homogeneous material characterisation. In (Singh et al., 2017), a three-ray reflection model is designed to characterize building materials assuming that the material under measurement has a fixed complex permittivity. In (Tian et al., 2019), infinite reflections inside the planar material have been taken into account. In general, the accuracy of computation depends

72 on the considered number of internal reflections and the position of the receiver. The im-
 73 pact of the number of internal reflections on the accuracy of a lossless board-shaped ma-
 74 terial is investigated in (Plouhinec & Uguen, 2011). When the high-order reflections can
 75 be neglected, a resolution of the first and the second rays facilitates simpler estimation
 76 algorithm for estimation of material's EM properties.

Figure 1. Multiple reflections of the measured board-shaped materials. θ_i denotes the incident angle.

77 In this paper, we focus on the characterization of the spatial resolution of the two-
 78 ray reflection model from planar building materials in the VNA-based measurement. The
 79 proposed algorithms and analysis is validated on actual material samples. However, re-
 80 solving closely adjacent arriving multipath components from measurement data is still
 81 challenging via inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) methodologies (Zheng et al., 2015;
 82 Yang et al., 2001; Tewari et al., 2014) due to their insufficient time domain resolution.
 83 In this paper, we propose a three-step minimum least squares (MLS) based algorithm
 84 to resolve two adjacent rays reflected from the front and the back surfaces of a board-
 85 shaped material. To overcome the problem of multiple local minima in conventional MLS
 86 based algorithms, the method of moments (MoM) (Kay, 1993) without optimality prop-
 87 erty is employed to obtain a rough estimate as the initial point of the iteration. The per-
 88 formance of the proposed algorithm is evaluated through comparison with the Cramér-
 89 Rao lower bound (CRLB). A closed-form expression of the CRLB is derived as a bench-
 90 mark of performance. Moreover, typical building materials, including a wooden board,
 91 a plaster board, and a granite board, are measured for various incident angles to vali-
 92 date the algorithm. Comparisons between the CRLB and measurements show that the
 93 proposed algorithm is capable of resolving two closely adjacent rays with an excellent
 94 accuracy.

95 It is worth noting that the proposed model is limited to cases where powers of the
 96 main reflection and the first-order internal reflection are much greater than that of the
 97 combination of high-order reflections, multipath components in the measurement envi-
 98 ronment, and measurement noise.

99 The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the system model
 100 and states the problem. In Section III, the MLS inspired algorithm is proposed. In Sec-
 101 tion IV, the CRLB is analytically derived in a closed-form expression as a benchmark
 102 of performance. In Section V, numerical results on the performance of the algorithm are
 103 provided. In Section VI, the algorithm is practically validated through measurements.
 104 Finally, Section VII concludes this paper.

105 2 Signal Model and Problem Statement

106 In order to properly characterize the signal contributions from indoor building struc-
 107 tures, e.g., board-shaped materials, we need to consider reflections and transmissions within

108 the material as shown in Fig. 1. As can be seen, the reflected EM waves are comprised
 109 by the direct reflection ray (named the first ray in the remainder of this paper) and the
 110 reflection ray from the back side of the board (denoted as the second ray). The measured
 111 S_{21} consists then of both these rays as well as high-order reflections inside the material,
 112 other multipath components in the measurement environment and measurement noise.
 113 In the mm-Wave band, since the attenuation of the EM waves in the material is high,
 114 we assume that only the first and the second rays are dominant, and high-order reflec-
 115 tions inside the material, other multipath components in the measurement environment,
 116 and measurement noise are much weaker than the first and the second rays. Therefore,
 117 the measured S_{21} is approximate to

$$S_{21}[n] \approx \Gamma_1[n] \exp(j\omega[n]r_1/c) + \Gamma_2[n] \exp[j(\omega[n]r_2/c + \phi)], \quad (1)$$

118 where r_1 and $r_2 = r_1 + 2\Delta d \operatorname{Re}(\sqrt{\epsilon_r - \sin^2 \theta_i})$ are the equivalent path lengths of the
 119 first and the second rays considering adjustment of the speed of light in the material,
 120 $\Gamma_1[n] \exp(j\omega[n]r_1/c)$ is the S_{21} parameter of the first ray and $\Gamma_2[n] \exp[j(\omega[n]r_2/c + \phi)]$
 121 is the S_{21} parameter of the second ray, $n = 1, 2, \dots, N_\omega$ is the index of frequency sam-
 122 ples, ϕ is the phase shift relative to the first ray, $c = 3 \times 10^8$ m/s is the speed of light.
 123 $\Gamma_1[n]$ and $\Gamma_2[n]$ are the real amplitudes of the first and the second rays at the surface
 124 of the material, respectively, whereas $\Delta r = r_2 - r_1$ is the equivalent path difference
 125 between the second and the first rays. According to the Friis transmission formula, the
 126 amplitudes $\Gamma_1[n]$ and $\Gamma_2[n]$ can be modelled to be inversely proportional to $\omega[n]$. Hence,
 127 we assume that $\Gamma_1[n] = \gamma_1/\omega[n] \times 10^9$, $\Gamma_2[n] = \gamma_2/\omega[n] \times 10^9$, where

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{0.3\sqrt{G_t G_r} |\Gamma|}{2r_1}, \quad (2)$$

128 and

$$\gamma_2 = \frac{0.3\sqrt{G_t G_r} |\Gamma| |T|^2 \exp(-4\alpha L)}{2r_2} \quad (3)$$

129 are two scaling factors, where Γ and T denote the reflection coefficient and the trans-
 130 mission coefficient of the surface, respectively. α denotes the attenuation constant, G_t
 131 and G_r denote gains of the transmit and the receive measurement antennas, respectively.
 132 L denotes the effective thickness of the material under measurement (Singh et al., 2017,
 133 Eq. (1)).

134 To validate that the first and the second rays are dominant, a comparison of the
 135 two-ray model with the infinite-reflection model (Tian et al., 2019) is illustrated in Fig.
 136 2, where $\Gamma = -0.2$, $T = 1 + \Gamma = 0.8$, $\exp(-4\alpha L) = 0.6$, $G_t = G_r = 15.8$ dBi,
 137 $S_{21, \text{two-ray}}(\omega)$ is generated by (1), and

$$S_{21, \text{infinite-reflection}}(\omega) = \Gamma_1 \exp(j\omega r_1/c) + \sum_{n_r=2}^{\infty} \Gamma_{n_r} \exp[j(\omega r_{n_r}/c + n_r \phi)], \quad (4)$$

138 where $\Gamma_{n_r} = \gamma_{n_r}/\omega \times 10^9$ and $\gamma_{n_r} = \frac{0.3\sqrt{G_t G_r} |\Gamma|^{2n_r-1} |T|^2 \exp(-4\alpha L(n_r-1))}{2r_{n_r}}$.

139 It is observed that the contribution of the second ray is not negligible, and will be
 140 analyzed in this paper.

141 Furthermore, we use the infinity norm distance between S_{21} parameters generated
 142 by the two-ray model and the infinite-reflection model to evaluate the error introduced
 143 by neglecting high-order reflections, i.e.,

$$e = \max_{\omega \in \mathbb{R}^+} \{ |20 \log_{10} |S_{21, \text{infinite-reflection}}(\omega)| - 20 \log_{10} |S_{21, \text{two-ray}}(\omega)| | \}. \quad (5)$$

Figure 2. Comparison of the two-ray model with the infinite-reflections model, where $\gamma_1 = 1.14$, $\gamma_2 = 0.44$.

144 To avoid the brutal-force search of ω that leads to maximum distance between two S_{21}
 145 parameters, the error is upper bounded as

$$\begin{aligned}
 e &= \max_{\omega \in \mathbb{R}^+} \left\{ \left| 10 \log_{10} \left| \frac{\Gamma_1 \exp(j\omega r_1/c) + \sum_{n_r=2}^{\infty} \Gamma_{n_r} \exp[j(\omega r_{n_r}/c + n_r \phi)]}{\Gamma_1 \exp(j\omega r_1/c) + \Gamma_2 \exp[j(\omega r_2/c + \phi)]} \right| \right| \right\} \\
 &\leq \max_{\omega \in \mathbb{R}^+} \left\{ \left| 10 \log_{10} \left| 1 + \frac{\sum_{n_r=3}^{\infty} \Gamma_{n_r}}{\Gamma_1 - \Gamma_2} \right| \right| \right\} \\
 &\triangleq e_U.
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

146 The error upper bound e_U is illustrated in Fig. 3. From Fig. 3, we observe that the er-
 147 ror upper bound is less than 0.3 dB at all frequency bands, and the contribution of high-
 148 order rays is slight in comparison with two dominant rays and thus are negligible.

149 Discerning the two closely adjacent rays is not straightforward in practice. Tradition-
 150 ally, properties of reflection rays are estimated through IFFT based algorithms from
 151 frequency domain measurements (Zheng et al., 2015). However, the resolution capabil-
 152 ity of the measurement is constrained by the measurement bandwidth B in IFFT based
 153 algorithms. When $\Delta r < \frac{c}{B}$, the two rays in (1) are not resolvable. Therefore, for a mater-
 154 ial whose thickness Δd is smaller than $c/(2 \cos(\theta_i) B \sqrt{\epsilon_r})$ with ϵ_r denoting the relative
 155 permittivity of the material, the two adjacent rays are not resolvable by IFFT. Even
 156 if the measurement bandwidth is as large as 10 GHz, the corresponding resolution of Δr
 157 is only 3 cm, which is comparable to the thickness of the measured material. It is dif-
 158 ficult to distinguish them in the time domain, because of the side lobes introduced by
 159 the IFFT with rectangular window in the frequency domain (Aditya et al., 2018, Fig.
 160 4). Example of channel impulse response (CIR) computed by IFFT from simulated $S_{21}[n]$
 161 without noise are shown in Fig. 4 for various Δr , where $\gamma_1 = 1$, $\gamma_2 = 0.4$, and $\phi_0 =$
 162 π . We observe that since $\Delta r \leq 4$ cm, the two rays appear as a single ray after IFFT
 163 from $S_{21}[n]$, and they are not distinguishable through IFFT based algorithms.

Figure 3. Error upper bound computed by (6).

Figure 4. An example of IFFT based two ray resolution, where $\gamma_1 = 1$, $\gamma_2 = 0.4$, and $\phi_0 = \pi$.

164 **3 Reflection Rays Resolution**

165 To overcome the above problem, an algorithm to separate the two rays is presented
 166 in the following.

167 First, the receive power in the two-ray model is computed

$$|S_{21}[n]|^2 = \Gamma_1[n]^2 + \Gamma_2[n]^2 + 2\Gamma_1[n]\Gamma_2[n] \cos(\omega[n]\Delta r/c + \phi). \quad (7)$$

168 Now, multiplying both sides of (7) by $\omega^2[n]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} y[n] &= |S_{21}[n]|^2 \omega^2[n] \\ &= \gamma_1^2 + \gamma_2^2 + 2\gamma_1\gamma_2 \cos(\omega[n]\Delta r/c + \phi) + P_m[n], \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

169 where $P_m[n]$ is the error introduced by the other multipath components and noise. Since
 170 the first and the second rays are dominant, it can be assumed that the combined effect
 171 of the other multipath components and noise behave like white noise, i.e., $P_m[n] \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_m^2)$,
 172 and $\sigma_m^2 \ll \gamma_i^2, i = 1, 2$.

173 In order to extract unknown parameters of both rays from the measured S_{21} , i.e.,
 174 $[\hat{\gamma}_1, \hat{\gamma}_2, \Delta \hat{r}, \hat{\phi}]$, we propose an MLS method inspired algorithm. The basic mechanism of
 175 the MLS method is to minimize the mean square distance between the measured and

176 the estimated S_{21} parameters, i.e.

$$[\hat{\gamma}_1, \hat{\gamma}_2, \Delta\hat{r}, \hat{\phi}] = \arg \min \left\{ \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{N_f} |F(\hat{\gamma}_1, \hat{\gamma}_2, \Delta\hat{r}, \hat{\phi}, n) - y[n]|^2}{N_f} \right\}, \quad (9)$$

177 where

$$F(\hat{\gamma}_1, \hat{\gamma}_2, \Delta\hat{r}, \hat{\phi}, n) = \hat{\gamma}_1^2 + \hat{\gamma}_2^2 + 2\hat{\gamma}_1\hat{\gamma}_2 \cos(\omega[n]\Delta\hat{r}/c + \hat{\phi}). \quad (10)$$

178 It is worthwhile to note that (9) is a non-linear least squares problem.

Figure 5. An example of $|F(\hat{\gamma}_1, \hat{\gamma}_2, \Delta\hat{r}, \hat{\phi}, n) - y[n]|^2$. At $\Delta r = 3$ cm, a slight error still exists due to the combination of high-order reflections inside the material, other multipath components in the measurement environment, and measurement noise, which are modeled as P_m in (5).

179 An example of the variation of $|F(\hat{\gamma}_1, \hat{\gamma}_2, \Delta\hat{r}, \hat{\phi}, n) - y[n]|^2$ as a function of $\Delta\hat{r}$ is
 180 plotted in Fig. 5, where $\hat{\gamma}_1 = \gamma_1 = 1$, $\hat{\gamma}_2 = \gamma_2 = 0.1$, $\hat{\phi} = \phi = \pi$, $\Delta r = 0.03$ m,
 181 and $\sigma_m^2 = 10^{-2}$. It is observed from Fig. 5 that the optimization can have numerous
 182 local minima. Therefore, given an inappropriate choice of initial points of iteration, an
 183 estimate of Δr may lead to a local minima of $|F(\hat{\gamma}_1, \hat{\gamma}_2, \Delta\hat{r}, \hat{\phi}, n) - y[n]|^2$ instead of the
 184 the optimum estimate by implementing the conventional MLS method (Stoica et al., 1989).
 185 With a local best estimate of Δr , optimum estimates of other parameters could neither
 186 be obtained. However, performing an exhaustive search in (9) to jointly estimate $[\hat{\gamma}_1, \hat{\gamma}_2, \Delta\hat{r}, \hat{\phi}]$
 187 is computational too expensive.

188 Thus, in order to reduce the computational complexity, we first estimate the $[\check{\gamma}_1, \check{\gamma}_2]$
 189 and $[\Delta\check{r}, \check{\phi}]$, separately in the first two steps to obtain rough estimates. Then, we use the
 190 rough estimates $[\check{\gamma}_1, \check{\gamma}_2, \Delta\check{r}, \check{\phi}]$ as an input into the conventional MLS estimator to obtain
 191 $[\hat{\gamma}_1, \hat{\gamma}_2, \Delta\hat{r}, \hat{\phi}]$. The steps are explained in the following.

192 **Step 1:** We estimate $[\check{\gamma}_1, \check{\gamma}_2]$ using the MoM first. By defining

$$\begin{cases} \mu_0 = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{N_f} y[n]}{N_f}, \\ \mu_k = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{N_f-k} y[n]y[n+k]}{N_f-k}, k = 1, 2, \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

193 we obtain

$$\begin{cases} E[\mu_0] = \gamma_1^2 + \gamma_2^2, \\ E[\mu_k] = (\gamma_1^2 + \gamma_2^2)^2 + 2\gamma_1^2\gamma_2^2 \cos(k\Delta\omega\Delta r/c). \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

194 Following manipulations in Appendix A, we obtain the MoM estimators of $[\check{\gamma}_1, \check{\gamma}_2]$ from
 195 (12) as

$$\begin{cases} \check{\gamma}_1 = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0 + \sqrt{\mu_0^2 - 4A}}{2}}, \\ \check{\gamma}_2 = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0 - \sqrt{\mu_0^2 - 4A}}{2}}, \\ A = \frac{-\mu'_2 + \sqrt{\mu'_2{}^2 + 8\mu_1'^2}}{4}, \\ \mu'_k = \mu_k - \mu_0^2. \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

196 **Step 2:** We estimate the $[\Delta\check{r}, \check{\phi}]$ using the estimated $[\check{\gamma}_1, \check{\gamma}_2]$. Hence, substituting
 197 $[\check{\gamma}_1, \check{\gamma}_2]$ from (13) into (9), we obtain

$$\begin{cases} [\Delta\check{r}, \check{\phi}] = \arg \min \left\{ \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{N_f} |z[n] - \cos(\omega[n]\Delta\check{r}/c + \check{\phi})|^2}{N_f} \right\}, \\ z[n] = \frac{y[n] - \check{\gamma}_1^2 - \check{\gamma}_2^2}{2\check{\gamma}_1\check{\gamma}_2}. \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

198 The estimates of $[\Delta\check{r}, \check{\phi}]$ are then obtained from measurement data by exhaustive search.

Figure 6. Examples of resolution, where $\gamma_1 = 1$, $\gamma_2 = 0.4$, and $\phi_0 = \pi$. The measurements are generated by (5).

199 **Step 3:** Using the output of steps 1-2 as an initial point, we obtain the final es-
 200 timation $[\hat{\gamma}_1, \hat{\gamma}_2, \hat{\Delta r}, \hat{\phi}]$ using the well-known conventional nonlinear least square method
 201 (LSM). In this paper we use the *lsqcurvefit* function in MATLAB 2018a software from
 202 Mathworks (Mathworks, 2019).

203 As an example, the amplitudes of $S_{21}[n]$ before and after applying the proposed
 204 estimation algorithm are shown in Fig. 6, where $\gamma_1 = 1$, $\gamma_2 = 0.4$, and $\phi_0 = \pi$. From

205 Fig. 6, we observe that even though the Δr is as small as 2 cm, the algorithm is capa-
 206 ble of resolving the two closely adjacent rays with excellent accuracy.

207 4 Cramér-Rao Lower Bound

208 From (8), the joint probability density function (PDF) of $y[n]$ is represented as (15)
 209 given $[\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \Delta r, \phi, \sigma_m]$.

$$P(y[1], \dots, y[N_f]; \gamma_1, \gamma_2, \Delta r, \phi) = \frac{\exp\left[-\frac{\sum_{n=1}^{N_f} (\gamma_1^2 + \gamma_2^2 + 2\gamma_1\gamma_2 \cos(\omega[n]\Delta r/c + \phi) - y[n])^2}{2\sigma_m^2}\right]}{(2\pi\sigma_m^2)^{\frac{N_f}{2}}}. \quad (15)$$

210 The Fisher information matrix of the estimator, $\mathbf{I}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \Delta r, \phi)$, then is computed by

$$\mathbf{I}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \Delta r, \phi) = \frac{1}{\sigma_m^2} \sum_{n=1}^{N_f} \begin{bmatrix} I_{\gamma_1}^2[n] & I_{\gamma_1}[n]I_{\gamma_2}[n] & I_{\gamma_1}[n]I_{\Delta r}[n] & I_{\gamma_1}[n]I_{\phi}[n] \\ I_{\gamma_2}[n]I_{\gamma_1}[n] & I_{\gamma_2}^2[n] & I_{\gamma_2}[n]I_{\Delta r}[n] & I_{\gamma_2}[n]I_{\phi}[n] \\ I_{\Delta r}[n]I_{\gamma_1}[n] & I_{\Delta r}[n]I_{\gamma_2}[n] & I_{\Delta r}^2[n] & I_{\Delta r}[n]I_{\phi}[n] \\ I_{\phi}[n]I_{\gamma_1}[n] & I_{\phi}[n]I_{\gamma_2}[n] & I_{\phi}[n]I_{\Delta r}[n] & I_{\phi}^2[n] \end{bmatrix}, \quad (16)$$

211 where

$$\begin{cases} I_{\gamma_1}[n] = 2\gamma_1 + 2\gamma_2 \cos(\omega[n]\Delta r/c + \phi), \\ I_{\gamma_2}[n] = 2\gamma_2 + 2\gamma_1 \cos(\omega[n]\Delta r/c + \phi), \\ I_{\Delta r}[n] = -\frac{2\gamma_1\gamma_2\omega[n] \sin(\frac{\omega[n]\Delta r}{c} + \phi)}{c}, \\ I_{\phi}[n] = -2\gamma_1\gamma_2 \sin\left(\frac{\omega[n]\Delta r}{c} + \phi\right). \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

212 Therefore, from (16), the CRLB of estimating $[\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \Delta r, \phi]$ is given in a closed-
 213 form expression by

$$\begin{cases} \text{CRLB}(\hat{\gamma}_1) = [\mathbf{I}^{-1}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \Delta r, \phi)]_{11} = \frac{G_{\hat{\gamma}_1}}{\sigma_m^2 G}, \\ \text{CRLB}(\hat{\gamma}_2) = [\mathbf{I}^{-1}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \Delta r, \phi)]_{22} = \frac{G_{\hat{\gamma}_2}}{\sigma_m^2 G}, \\ \text{CRLB}(\hat{\Delta r}) = [\mathbf{I}^{-1}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \Delta r, \phi)]_{33} = \frac{G_{\hat{\Delta r}}}{\sigma_m^2 G}, \\ \text{CRLB}(\hat{\phi}) = [\mathbf{I}^{-1}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \Delta r, \phi)]_{44} = \frac{G_{\hat{\phi}}}{\sigma_m^2 G}, \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

214 where $G_{\hat{\gamma}_1}$, $G_{\hat{\gamma}_2}$, $G_{\Delta\hat{r}}$, $G_{\hat{\phi}}$, and G are computed by

$$\begin{cases}
 G_{\hat{\gamma}_1} = \det \left\{ \sum_{n=1}^{N_f} \begin{bmatrix} I_{\gamma_2}^2[n] & I_{\gamma_2}[n]I_{\Delta r}[n] & I_{\gamma_2}[n]I_{\phi}[n] \\ I_{\Delta r}[n]I_{\gamma_2}[n] & I_{\Delta r}^2[n] & I_{\Delta r}[n]I_{\phi}[n] \\ I_{\phi}[n]I_{\gamma_2}[n] & I_{\phi}[n]I_{\Delta r}[n] & I_{\phi}^2[n] \end{bmatrix} \right\}, \\
 G_{\hat{\gamma}_2} = \det \left\{ \sum_{n=1}^{N_f} \begin{bmatrix} I_{\gamma_1}^2[n] & I_{\gamma_1}[n]I_{\Delta r}[n] & I_{\gamma_1}[n]I_{\phi}[n] \\ I_{\Delta r}[n]I_{\gamma_1}[n] & I_{\Delta r}^2[n] & I_{\Delta r}[n]I_{\phi}[n] \\ I_{\phi}[n]I_{\gamma_1}[n] & I_{\phi}[n]I_{\Delta r}[n] & I_{\phi}^2[n] \end{bmatrix} \right\}, \\
 G_{\Delta\hat{r}} = \det \left\{ \sum_{n=1}^{N_f} \begin{bmatrix} I_{\gamma_1}^2[n] & I_{\gamma_1}[n]I_{\gamma_2}[n] & I_{\gamma_1}[n]I_{\phi}[n] \\ I_{\gamma_2}[n]I_{\gamma_1}[n] & I_{\gamma_2}^2[n] & I_{\gamma_2}[n]I_{\phi}[n] \\ I_{\phi}[n]I_{\gamma_1}[n] & I_{\phi}[n]I_{\gamma_2}[n] & I_{\phi}^2[n] \end{bmatrix} \right\}, \\
 G_{\hat{\phi}} = \det \left\{ \sum_{n=1}^{N_f} \begin{bmatrix} I_{\gamma_1}^2[n] & I_{\gamma_1}[n]I_{\gamma_2}[n] & I_{\gamma_1}[n]I_{\Delta r}[n] \\ I_{\gamma_2}[n]I_{\gamma_1}[n] & I_{\gamma_2}^2[n] & I_{\gamma_2}[n]I_{\Delta r}[n] \\ I_{\Delta r}[n]I_{\gamma_1}[n] & I_{\Delta r}[n]I_{\gamma_2}[n] & I_{\Delta r}^2[n] \end{bmatrix} \right\}, \\
 G = \det \left\{ \sum_{n=1}^{N_f} \begin{bmatrix} I_{\gamma_1}^2[n] & I_{\gamma_1}[n]I_{\gamma_2}[n] & I_{\gamma_1}[n]I_{\Delta r}[n] & I_{\gamma_1}[n]I_{\phi}[n] \\ I_{\gamma_2}[n]I_{\gamma_1}[n] & I_{\gamma_2}^2[n] & I_{\gamma_2}[n]I_{\Delta r}[n] & I_{\gamma_2}[n]I_{\phi}[n] \\ I_{\Delta r}[n]I_{\gamma_1}[n] & I_{\Delta r}[n]I_{\gamma_2}[n] & I_{\Delta r}^2[n] & I_{\Delta r}[n]I_{\phi}[n] \\ I_{\phi}[n]I_{\gamma_1}[n] & I_{\phi}[n]I_{\gamma_2}[n] & I_{\phi}[n]I_{\Delta r}[n] & I_{\phi}^2[n] \end{bmatrix} \right\},
 \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

215 where $\det(\mathbf{X})$ denotes the determinant of the matrix \mathbf{X} , and \mathbf{X}_{mn} denotes the element
 216 in the m -th row and the n -th column. In the numerical result section, the CRLB is em-
 217 ployed as a performance benchmark of the three-step LMS algorithm presented here.

218 5 Numerical Results

219 Fig. 6 validated that the algorithm is capable of resolving the two closely adjacent
 220 rays. Indeed, the mean square error (MSE) of the proposed algorithm is compared with
 221 the CRLB computed by (18) in Fig. 7. For low the power of high-order reflections and
 222 other multipath components in the measurement environment, i.e., σ_m^2 , the proposed al-
 223 gorithm has an MSE that is close to the CRLB. Therefore, environments with less scat-
 224 ters are preferred to carry out the measurement.

225 From Fig. 7, we also observe that the performance of the algorithm depends on ϕ .
 226 The impact of ϕ on the CRLBs is illustrated in Fig. 8, where we observe that CRLBs
 227 are periodic functions of ϕ . For the measurement of a board-shaped material, when $\Delta r =$
 228 $2\Delta d \text{Re}(\sqrt{\epsilon_r - \sin^2 \theta_i})$ changes, the value of $\omega[n]\Delta r/c$ changes rapidly at the mmWave
 229 band due to a large $\omega[n]$. From (17), we further observe that for a slight change of Δr ,
 230 the change of $\omega[n]\Delta r/c$, with a relatively large value, is added onto ϕ , which has a limit
 231 range of $(0, 2\pi]$. Therefore, in the RL/RT-based channel simulation, ϕ can be assumed
 232 as a uniformly distributed variable. To shed some light on the impact of the length dif-
 233 ference Δr on the average MSE of the proposed estimators, we use the metric average
 234 CRLB (ACRLB) for each estimated parameter, which are defined as

$$\begin{cases}
 \text{ACRLB}(\hat{\gamma}_1) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \text{CRLB}(\hat{\gamma}_1) d\phi, \\
 \text{ACRLB}(\hat{\gamma}_2) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \text{CRLB}(\hat{\gamma}_2) d\phi, \\
 \text{ACRLB}(\Delta\hat{r}) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \text{CRLB}(\Delta\hat{r}) d\phi, \\
 \text{ACRLB}(\hat{\phi}) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \text{CRLB}(\hat{\phi}) d\phi.
 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

235 In Fig. 9, the ACRLB versus Δr is plotted. Therein, only ACRLBs are given be-
 236 cause the proposed algorithm is CRLB-achieving, and simulating the algorithm for all
 237 possible ϕ is too computational expensive. From Fig. 9, we observe that 1) the ACRLB
 238 decreases with an increasing Δr because the two rays are more easier to be distinguished

Figure 7. MSE of the estimators, where $\gamma_1 = 1$, $\gamma_2 = 0.4$, and $\Delta r = 3$ cm. Markers are simulation results from 3000 realizations, and solid lines denote the CRLB computed by (18).

239 with a large Δr , and 2) even though the Δr is large, the ACRLB can not be infinitely
 240 small due to the existence of multipath components but has a floor, which can be com-
 241 puted following some trivial derivations by letting $\Delta r \rightarrow +\infty$ as

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{CRLB}_f(\hat{\gamma}_1) = \frac{2\sigma_m^2\gamma_2^2 + \sigma_m^2\gamma_1^2}{K_1}, \\ \text{CRLB}_f(\hat{\gamma}_2) = \frac{2\sigma_m^2\gamma_1^2 + \sigma_m^2\gamma_2^2}{K_1}, \\ \text{CRLB}_f(\Delta\hat{r}) = \frac{N_f\sigma_m^2\gamma_1^2\gamma_2^2}{K_2}, \\ \text{CRLB}_f(\hat{\phi}) = \frac{\sigma_m^2\gamma_1^2\gamma_2^2 \sum_{n=1}^{N_f} \omega^2[n]}{c^2 K_2}, \end{array} \right. \quad (21)$$

242 where

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} K_1 = 4N_f(\gamma_1^4 + \gamma_2^4 - 2\gamma_1^2\gamma_2^2), \\ K_2 = \frac{2\gamma_1^4\gamma_2^4 \left[N_f \sum_{n=1}^{N_f} \omega^2[n] - \left(\sum_{n=1}^{N_f} \omega[n] \right)^2 \right]}{c^2}. \end{array} \right. \quad (22)$$

243 6 Measurement Validation

244 In order to validate the algorithm, a measurement campaign was performed on vari-
 245 ous typical building structure materials, as shown in Fig. 10. In the system, a VNA is
 246 employed to measure the $S_{21}[n]$ of the propagation channel via reflection from the anal-
 247 ysed materials, $n = 1, 2, \dots, N_f$. In this paper, the measurements are carried out at 40-
 248 50 GHz and with $N_f = 41$. Hence, $\omega[n] = 80\pi + (n-1)\Delta\omega$ Grad/s, $\Delta\omega = 0.5\pi$
 249 Grad/s. Two horn antennas with a same gain of 15.8 dBi and a 3 dB beam width of 0.25
 250 rad are connected to the VNA via cables to transmit and receive TE polarized waves.

Figure 8. The impact of ϕ on CRLBs of the estimators $\hat{\gamma}_1$, $\hat{\gamma}_2$, $\hat{\phi}$, and $\Delta\hat{r}$ where $\gamma_1 = 1$, $\gamma_2 = 0.4$, $\Delta r = 2$ cm and $\sigma_m = 0.1$.

251 The radiation patterns of the antennas are shown in Fig. 10(c). The cable losses are 20
 252 dB at 45 GHz. To remove the combined response of coaxial cable and connectors, the
 253 VNA is calibrated by standard 2-port SOLT calibration method. With high directivity,
 254 the horn antennas effectively reduce the interference from unwanted directions efficiently.
 255 A laptop is used to collect and analyse the data from the VNA.

256 The considered typical materials of building structures are a wooden board, a plaster
 257 board and a granite board. The thickness of the measured materials is less than 2
 258 cm. Considering 10λ distance as the boundary of the far field, it is then equal to 7.5 cm
 259 at 40 GHz and 6 cm at 50 GHz. Therefore, the distance between the antennas and the
 260 reflection position is 50 cm that satisfies the far-field condition of the considered frequency
 261 band. Our examples consider two incident angles, i.e., $\theta_i \in \{\frac{\pi}{6}, \frac{\pi}{3}\}$.

Table 1. Measured parameters.

Material	θ_i	$\hat{\gamma}_1$	$\hat{\gamma}_2$	$\Delta\hat{r}$ [cm]	$\hat{\phi}$ [rad]	$\hat{\sigma}_m$
Wooden board	$\pi/6$	0.49	0.20	2.50	-0.19	0.05
	$\pi/3$	0.45	0.19	3.34	-0.33	0.03
Plaster board	$\pi/6$	0.44	0.20	2.53	2.25	0.03
	$\pi/3$	0.28	0.13	2.67	4.76	0.02
Granite	$\pi/6$	0.71	0.23	6.34	-1.84	0.08
	$\pi/3$	0.54	0.24	7.06	1.42	0.04

262 Using the measured data, results of two rays resolution using the proposed algo-
 263 rithm are given in Table 1 and illustrated in Fig. 11. From (8), the estimated $\hat{\sigma}_m$ is ob-

Figure 9. ACRLBs of the estimators $\hat{\gamma}_1$, $\hat{\gamma}_2$, $\hat{\phi}$, and $\Delta\hat{r}$ where $\gamma_1 = 1$ and $\sigma_m = 0.1$.

Figure 10. Measurement set-up: equipment, measurement scenario, and considered materials.

264 tained by

$$\hat{\sigma}_m = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_f} \sum_{n=1}^{N_f} \left[|S_{21}[n]|^2 \omega^2[n] - \hat{\gamma}_1^2 - \hat{\gamma}_2^2 \right]^2 - 2\hat{\gamma}_1 \hat{\gamma}_2 \cos(\omega[n] \Delta\hat{r}/c + \hat{\phi})}, \quad (23)$$

265 It is observed that the estimated $\hat{\sigma}_m$ from measurements is less than 0.1 and combina-
 266 tion of the separated rays matches the measured S_{21} parameter very well.

267 It is worth noting that more incident angles have to be considered in measurements
 268 using the proposed MLS based algorithm in the future. To support the RL/RT algorithms,
 269 appropriate empirical characterization of the two-ray model is required to support RL/RT-
 270 based channel models.

Figure 11. Results of two ray resolution from measurements with two incident angles, i.e., $\theta_i \in \{\frac{\pi}{6}, \frac{\pi}{3}\}$. Typical building materials, i.e., a wooden board, a plaster board and a granite board are measured.

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7 Conclusions

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A three-step minimum least squares (MLS) inspired algorithm to resolve two adjacent rays for board-shaped material EM property measurement is proposed with the assumption that powers of the main reflection and the first-order internal reflection are much greater than that of the combination of high-order reflections, multipath components in the measurement environment, and measurement noise. The performance of the proposed algorithm is shown to be close to the Cramér-Rao lower Bound (CRLB). The proposed algorithm is validated by measurements of typical board-shaped building materials, e.g., wooden board, plaster board, and granite, are measured. The analysis shows that the algorithm is capable of resolving two closely adjacent rays with an excellent accuracy from measurement at the mmWave frequencies, e.g., 40-50 GHz. The proposed algorithm can be applied in the measurement based board-shaped building material characterization. In the future, more building materials will be measured and characterized under various incident angles through measurements using the proposed algorithm. A database will be established accordingly. Based on the data base, empirical two-ray building material reflection models will be built and integrated in RT/RL based channel models, which can be applied in the prediction, simulation and analysis of electromagnetic wave propagation in indoor environments at the millimeter-wave frequencies for 5G and other emerging wireless systems.

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Appendix A Proof of (13)

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From (12), the MoM estimators for γ_1 , γ_2 , ϕ , and Δr are defined as the solution to the simultaneous equations

$$\begin{cases} \mu_0 = \gamma_1^2 + \gamma_2^2, \\ \mu_k = (\gamma_1^2 + \gamma_2^2)^2 + 2\gamma_1^2\gamma_2^2 \cos(k\Delta\omega\Delta r/c). \end{cases} \quad (\text{A1})$$

293 By defining $\mu'_k = \mu_k - \mu_0^2$, we have

$$\begin{cases} \mu'_1 = 2\gamma_1^2\gamma_2^2 \cos(\Delta\omega\Delta r/c), \\ \mu'_2 = 2\gamma_1^2\gamma_2^2 [2\cos^2(\Delta\omega\Delta r/c) - 1]. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A2})$$

294 Substituting μ'_1 into μ'_2 , we obtain

$$\mu'_2 = \frac{\mu_1'^2}{\gamma_1^2\gamma_2^2} - 2\gamma_1^2\gamma_2^2. \quad (\text{A3})$$

295 Combining solve the equations (A3) and $\mu_0 = \gamma_1^2 + \gamma_2^2$, we obtain (13).

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301 The data are deposited in a public accessible domain and can be found in the link
302 below: https://figshare.com/articles/Data_that_supports_Two-Ray_Reflection_Resolution_Algorithm_for_Thin_Planar_Material_Electromagnetic_Property_Measurement_at_the_Millimeter-Wave_Bands_/9594569
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